

PECULIARITIES OF THE COMPANY'S STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

In this article, based on the latest literary sources, such an actual issue of management theory and practice as the peculiarities of the company's strategic management of human resources in Georgia is studied.

The role of strategic management of human resources on the effective functioning of companies is analyzed based on the data obtained as a result of the research of companies. Factors affecting/obstructing the strategic management of companies have been identified. The role of human resource management specialists in the success of companies and their importance from the employees' point of view are evaluated and analyzed.

Companies with a strategic human resources management plan and those without a strategic management plan are compared and the practices in them are analyzed according to organizational functions, which ultimately determine the human resources management policy in the companies.

Keywords: human resources, strategic management of human resources, intellectual capital, strategic thinking, recruiting, outsourcing, senior HR specialist, HR consultant, HR administrator.

Introduction

Today, the strategic management of human resources is a global challenge and, in this regard, Georgia is no exception.

In the conditions of modern increased competition, companies face the necessity of strategic management of human resources. Any company, in turn, tries to be competitive in the market and have a well-organized work culture. At the same time, the heads of the companies try to create effective systems of employee motivation in order to successfully operate the business. However, there are factors, and their action prevents the implementation of activities related to strategic management and creates a barrier to the effective functioning of the business.

In this regard, if we compare today's competitiveness of companies with 10-15 years ago, we will find a significant difference. In particular, we will see that the importance of factors such as technology, finance, production process, etc. has significantly decreased and, on the contrary, the role of human resources and capital has increased. Thus, the study of the problem of strategic management of the company's human resources is very necessary and contemporary.

Research methodology

In order to study the mentioned problem in detail, research was carried out in 30 companies operating in Georgia (large, medium, small). One human resource (HR) specialist or a person working in this direction from each company was involved in the research, who places the HR function in the company. The research questions were related to the activities of HR services as well as their involvement in the strategic work process of the organization.

The purpose of the research was to study the strategic management of human resources as a factor of the company's effectiveness. To achieve the set goal, the following tasks were defined: study of the company's human resources management policy; revealing the relationship between the strategy of human resources

management and the strategy of the organization; research on the role of human resource management managers in companies and their impact on business results; identifying the hindering factors and challenges in the company's human resources management process; determining the influence of the strategic human resource management plan on the rate of employee turnover.

Based on the research objectives, strategic human resource management was defined as a long-term development approach to human resource management (HRM) through the implementation of HR programs aimed at solving business issues and directly involved in ensuring long-term business goals.

Research results

As a result of the conducted research, the existing barriers were identified, which prevent human resources management specialists from performing HR functions.

It has been established that in today's competitive environment, it is difficult for an organization to succeed without a well-developed strategic plan that focuses on both short and long-term visions of the organization. A business with only a short-term vision is doomed to failure. This forces companies to have a competitive strategy, which means that the execution of planned activities is effective (Armstrong, 2017). Strategic thinking requires managers to take a long-term view of the business and the competitive environment together (Daft, 2010). In general, strategy ensures effective achievement of business results.

Having a strategy is equally important for large, medium and small companies. Of all surveyed companies, small (the average annual number of employees does not exceed 50 employees) - 15%, medium (the average annual number of employees varies from 50 to 250 people) - 52%, large (the average annual number of employees exceeds 249 people) - 33%.

Most of them (65%) have a strategic development plan according to individual departments/divisions. This fact confirms that most companies analyze the importance of strategy. However, 35% of companies do

not have a strategic plan by department/division at all. In such a case, it can be said that the work of the companies has a chaotic character. If we take into account the fact that within the scope of the research, companies of this type were distinguished by a large number of employees, the personnel management takes on an even more chaotic appearance. Therefore, we can say that today, the idea of the need to have a strategic human resources plan in the management of companies is still in its infancy.

In order to ensure the high effectiveness of the strategy, it is necessary that the information is clearly and comprehensibly delivered to each person who can influence the business results during the implementation of the strategy. Such a relationship helps to rationally deliver the strategy to the parties involved in the management process and creates the basis for the successful implementation of business plans. In this regard, the role of human resource management managers (SHRM) is particularly important in the process of forming business strategies. This means that SHRM has acquired vital importance and has become an important factor in business development.

According to the research, the HR manager is most often involved in the implementation of organizational strategies (70%) and focuses on strategic results (70%). In 63% of cases, he participates in the creation and development of the organizational strategy. In some cases, the HR manager is more involved in the development of business goals (33%) and the creation of organizational strategy (10%). However, in no case only 13% do not participate in the creation of organizational strategy.

As already mentioned, the existence of a strategy is important not only at the general business level, but also at the level of individual departments and divisions, which will be consistent with the general strategy of the company. In this regard, it is important for companies to have a well-formed human resources development strategy and plan.

Today, small and medium-sized enterprises focus more on human resource development than before, because due to sudden changes, human resources have become a strategic factor that affects the success of companies. Indeed, employees' intellectual capital, knowledge and competence determine the success or failure of a business in a dynamic environment (Ceranik & Popovic, 2010).

Consequently, HRM issues have become relevant for business for several reasons: first, because HRM is considered a top priority; second, HRM is of particular interest because human resources play a vital role in building sustainable competitive advantage; third, especially in small companies, the workforce plays an essential role (Bamberger, Biron, & Mashoulam, 2014).

Therefore, the existence of the HR institution becomes crucial in the formulation of the human resource management policy. The majority of surveyed companies (80%) have a strategic human resources plan. Only 20% of surveyed companies do not have a strategic plan. Along with the strategy of individual departments, there is also a strategy of human resources management. More specifically, 92% of large companies

surveyed have a strategic HR plan, which is not surprising, as large companies have to make great efforts to maintain their positions in a competitive environment.

Comparing large and small companies, we can say that the office space, the different amount of employees and the level of production in a small company are small. Accordingly, the HR department is also similar. Being an HR specialist in a small company means taking on more roles than human resource management (Johnson, 2017). Large- and medium-sized companies are not inferior to small-sized companies by having a strategic HR plan. In the case of 83% of the surveyed small companies, the existence of a strategic HR plan was observed.

According to 85% of the respondents, HR is represented in their company as a department/department/specialist. The companies where the HR institute exists in some form are mostly medium or large sized companies. Working as an HR specialist in a large company means managing human resources, gaining experience and creating a corporate culture. However, managing a large number of personnel is associated with certain challenges and requires a creative approach from the manager.

As for the second part, in 15% of companies (mainly medium and small businesses) HR functions are distributed to one or more people who perform personnel management functions in combination. In practice, these responsibilities are largely distributed to administrative managers who are more likely to perform operational tasks than strategic ones. Moreover, they are less involved in the process of making strategic decisions.

Based on the above, we can conclude that in large companies, due to the large number of employees, there is a need for their complex management, which leads to the existence of HR as a separate unit.

The most effective way for HR to communicate strategic initiatives to employees is to discuss the same department's strategy in the context of the company's strategy. It is important for HR to actively participate in the development and implementation of both human resources and business strategy. If he is not involved in the formation of business initiatives and aligning strategies with them, then he will not be able to make strategic contributions and participate in initiatives related to business development.

Respondents who indicated that their companies have an HR function in some form, 70% of them have a strategic HR plan. This fact may also be explained by the fact that human resources management services are often managed by certified HR professionals, therefore, their theoretical and practical knowledge in the mentioned field is quite high, and experience itself determines that managers often consider human resources management as one of the strategic directions and the whole Efforts are being made in personnel development. From this we can conclude that the presence of the HR service in the company has a significant impact on the formation and development of the strategic HR plan.

It is established that the concept of strategic management of human resources implies compliance of HR

strategy with business strategy. Otherwise, it turns out that these two strategic directions develop in an unstructured and chaotic manner. The human resources management manager, along with the employee management and development functions, performs a number of duties. This is expressed in the formulation of business plans and goals, creation of organizational strategy and strategic mapping.

The research revealed the main directions in which the human resource management service is most often involved. According to the respondents, HR is most often involved in the creation of the full cycle of the organizational strategy - from planning to implementation. The service is involved in the implementation of the organizational strategy and focuses on strategic results, equally 70% - 70%, and in 63% of cases it participates in the creation of the organizational strategy and the development of business goals.

It should also be noted that the existence of HR does not mean that the process of managing employees is complete and includes all levels of management in terms of attracting, selecting, hiring, preparing job descriptions, developing and maintaining personnel.

The majority of respondents - 40% state that the human resources management process in their companies is perfect. In particular, 92.5% focus on recruitment and selection, 70% on motivation, 58% on training and development, and 55% on retention. However, when asked which specific functions they do not perform, a minority said they are sometimes not involved in the development of compensation and performance management and retention programs. In contrast, HR management in 35% of companies does not cover all areas of strategic management. Among them, they never engage in work/life program development, talent management, and success planning programs.

To perfect human resource management, managers play different roles in companies. In this regard, especially large companies, where several HRs work in different directions, are particularly outstanding. Unlike small companies, where one or at most two people manage several functions at the same time. In addition, HR roles in large organizations are divided according to the complexity of the activities to be performed and the level of responsibilities.

For example, let's consider the personnel employed in HR in managerial and non-managerial positions in the company. The perception of high-level human resource management managers is more general and strategic, while for middle and low-level human resource management managers, the priority is to communicate directly with people, help and support employees. HR managers coordinate and plan HR activities unlike HR executives. This allows them to engage employees in recruitment, benefits programs, training, labor disputes and other administrative needs.

Nowadays, companies are experiencing increasing growth and human resource management services are no exception in this regard. The role of human resources management consultants is also growing in companies with a special speed. They may specialize in various areas of HR, including benefits programs, employee initiatives and reward programs, changes in

company culture after mergers and acquisitions, employee motivation, retirement planning, recruiting, or other factors that companies address when outsourcing.

In addition, HR employees in companies work as recruiters, selection specialists, as well as in the direction of trainings and career development. For example, those who are experienced in building and developing relationships with people work as recruiters. However, their role also differs depending on the position. For example, executive recruiters delegate tasks to senior recruiters in finding and filling job opportunities. Those who possess both theoretical and practical knowledge of human management issues, work in training and development, etc.

The role of HR administrator is also quite relevant. This includes daily routine office work - preparation of orders, labor contracts, sometimes participates in the recruitment process. When researching the role of human resource management managers, the activities to be performed were combined into three main groups: senior HR specialist, HR advisor, HR administrator. The meanings of the proposed categories/roles were explained to the respondents in advance. 55% of the surveyed respondents perform the function of senior HR in the company. The advisor function - 15% and the administrative function - only 10%.

According to these data, it is confirmed that the traditional approach to human resource management is gradually undergoing a transformation to a strategic approach. Which is definitely a positive fact, although it must be noted that human resource management managers in companies do not work only in the direction of strategic planning. In fact, they combine administrative activities with the work of strategic content due to the shortage of personnel in the company.

The presence of a strategic approach in a company does not mean that the human resources and capital management process is perfect. A deficiency in management may be related to employee relations, motivational system creation, salary rates and less opportunities for development and encouraging employee initiative.

All of the above actually represent a barrier to the perfection of the processes. However, companies sometimes think that they are doing their job exceptionally well, communicating with their employees and ensuring that their employees' lifestyles are improved. However, this kind of perception often does not coincide with the real wishes and opinions of the employees. HR plays an especially important role in this matter. Initiatives, decisions on employee incentives, creation of a pleasant working environment belong to HR to a significant extent. However, HR performs a number of operational and strategic roles that are not only related to human resource management. For the past 20 years, the function of HR has been to provide administrative support to strategic services. In some companies, HR has to constantly prove that it plays a vital role for the organization.

Conclusion

In conclusion, from the results of the conducted research, it is clear that today's transformational business environment implies the existence of challenges in

human resources management. Despite the fact that HR services have acquired a strategic role in organizations in recent years, they still face a number of barriers in the work process in the face of rapid changes. The process of change is never-ending, therefore, HR management services need to perform additional activities in order to immediately respond to the changes and to respond appropriately to it.

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